

UNIQUE PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF COLLABORATIVE LEARNING

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Abstract. *This article discusses collaborative teaching, pedagogical possibilities of collaborative technologies, principles used in the process of collaborative teaching, and their specific aspects. The possibilities of collaborative technologies in the training of future teachers are revealed. The article serves as an important scientific resource for the scientific-pedagogical community, future teachers, pedagogues and researchers.*

Keywords: *collaborative, pedagogical cooperation, joint activity, communication, activity, students, future teachers, professors, team work, group work, work in pairs.*

In recent years, research in the field of modernization of the content of higher pedagogical education has reached a new level. The scope of research in the field of improving the quality of education has expanded. New approaches to professional development of future teachers are being promoted. In this sense, attention to the use of pedagogical strategies is also increasing. This makes it possible to interpret the view of education and technologies as a separate strategy. Accordingly, the need for new technologies and strategies for teaching future teachers is growing.

Today, based on the analysis of efforts to expand the methodological foundations of pedagogy, we were convinced of the importance of conducting research in the field of expanding the scope of collaborative education. The existence of the need to create a collaborative environment in the process of higher pedagogical education created a basis for our research of collaborative technologies and strategies in different directions. There is a new approach to the interpretation of the strategies used in the educational process within the framework of joint activities of teachers and students. Future teachers should have a perspective trajectory of intellectual and personal development in the process of acquiring knowledge related to their chosen profession. It is important that all directions of the higher pedagogical education process focus on the intellectual, professional and personal development of future teachers. The strategy of personal and professional development of future teachers embodies the goal of mastering the educational content of the educational process. It also includes support for students' career interests and feedback. The following can be indicated as the main principles of strategy selection:

1. Active and self-directed education.
2. Education based on students' life experiences and research practice.
3. Education aimed at developing reflexive activity of students.
4. In the educational process, priority is given to principles such as achieving the organization of education aimed at the implementation of interactivity and cooperation.

Educational strategies presented by experts are characterized by a variety of appearance and content. Today, it is recommended to use the following strategies in the educational process.

1. Self-directed learning strategy. This strategy involves goal-oriented development of future teachers or improvement of their specific qualities. In this process, the future teachers themselves reflect on the processes of independent development and its stages. The purpose of using this strategy is to help future teachers to gain self-awareness, self-evaluation, independent

control, initiative, perseverance, self-confidence. The use of this strategy in the process of higher pedagogical education allows to achieve efficiency.

2. Experimental teaching strategy. Students learn new information and practical results based on the analysis of their own and others' experiences. As a result, their reflexive activity accelerates. This strategy is effective in higher education.

3. Contextual teaching strategy. In this, students model their social qualities and perform learning activities.

4. Strategy for developing critical thinking. This strategy serves to form a personal opinion in students, to create situations to search for new information, to objectively evaluate the acquired information, as well as to change points of view with the help of new information. As a result, the competence of critical analysis of a large amount of information is formed in future teachers.

5. Communicative strategy of teaching. This strategy fosters interaction among a group of students in an open communication situation by modeling behavior based on conversational development. This strategy is widely used in the process of teaching courses on mother tongue teaching methods, theory and methods of educational work.

6. Partnership learning strategy. This strategy is used in the process of collaborative learning, which allows knowledge to be managed and used effectively.

Within this approach, collaborative technologies are part of the partnership learning strategy. The word collaborative is derived from the English language and means common, united, together. In the science of pedagogy, the term collaboration is used in the sense of cooperation, partnership. Under the concept of collaboration, it is understood that learners work together towards a common goal. In this process, the goal of mutual exchange of knowledge, joint learning and reaching an agreement is realized. Within the framework of the concept of collaborative teaching, it is understood the organization of the processes of students' work in groups, in this process a solution to specific problems is found together, specific tasks are performed or a product is created.

According to the famous pedagogue N.V. Pavelev, in the framework of collaborative, that is, joint education, the educational process is organized on the basis of strong relations between students and students or students and teachers. Participants of the educational process acquire knowledge and necessary competences on the basis of joint search for information, discussion and understanding of ideas. As a result of the organization of the collaborative teaching process, the possibilities of joint work of students in the lesson are expanded. As a result of cooperation, students are able to achieve the main goal and guaranteed result in the educational process. In recent years, educators have begun to turn to collaborative learning technology. Because the skills of pedagogical cooperation are extremely necessary for future teachers, they serve to form the competence of working together with students in the course of their future professional activities. It should be noted that the scientific sources on pedagogy use two terms that are very close to each other in terms of content and essence: cooperative teaching and collaborative teaching. Some pedagogues do not dwell enough on their description. Some experts contrast these concepts or interpret collaboration as a means of implementing cooperation. We will try to explain the meaning of the term cooperation and collaboration below.

Cooperation is manifested as a form of interpersonal relations, as well as a form of organization of activities and a set of actions. Its main difference from collaboration is that the pedagogical process consists in combining the capabilities and actions of the participants with a

view to achieving the main goal, and at the same time in the distribution of roles and functions among them. As a synonym of this term, the concepts of unity and joint movement are used.

Collaboration means working together to achieve a common goal, and in this process, important decisions are made on the basis of students' mutual exchange of ideas and knowledge, informing about reaching an agreement. The words cooperation and partnership are used as the main synonyms of collaboration.

Collaborative technologies, which are part of convenient teaching strategies, meet the following criteria:

- clearly defining the purpose of the learning module to be mastered and formulating the assignments in a purposeful way;
- ensuring that students complete these tasks during the educational process;
- relying on the experiences of students and professors in this process;
- such as taking into account the specific characteristics of the learning environment in the process of using collaborative technology.

According to J.Fraysina, collaborative learning means joint action and lifestyle. Within this technology, the subjects of the educational process feel responsible for their actions, and also respect the capabilities and contributions of their partners to the educational process. Such a point of view was also supported by A.V.Kulikov. Collaborative teaching is primarily an educational philosophy, and process subjects act on the principle that we work together, learn together, change together, and improve together.

Collaborative technologies serve to create natural learning situations. In this process, students' knowledge develops directly as a result of joint actions. As a result, they create favorable conditions for creative activity. In the process of collaborative teaching, future teachers will be able to share their opportunities among group members, use group work methods. They work together towards the main goal of learning and professional development. Students' educational activities consist of components such as openness, flexibility and independent development.

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